

Motivational Aspects Influencing the Choice for English Medium School in Delhi India

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ABSTRACT

The study was intended to investigate motivational aspects influencing the choice for English Medium schools. Data was collected with the help of a self-developed scale. 900 respondents from the nine English medium schools from the various parts of Delhi, India constituted the sample of the study. Findings revealed both intrinsic and extrinsic aspects of motivation that influence the choice for English medium schools.

INTRODUCTION

Motivation is the main reason to direct the behaviour of an individual towards a particular goal. An idea, observation, need, emotion, or organic state can produce motivation that stimulates a person towards the source of fulfillment of the need. The motivational state is characterized by needs and desires requiring satisfaction. Needs and desires are influenced by culture, society, lifestyle, etc. Choice for English medium

school is very much influenced by needs and desires emerged from culture, society, lifestyle, and future prospects. The rational aspects of motivation are closely associated with the utility functions. This implies that choice for English medium schools will also be influenced by utility functions of the school as well as affective aspects that emerge from socio-cultural environment and lifestyle. Similarly the learning performance inside the school is also influenced by both cognitive (rational/utility) and affective (emotional)

aspects. Kraft, Sarogi, Husman, Semken, and Fuhrman (2018) emphasized on affective aspects of motivation for better learning performance. They said, "To motivate student learning, the affective domain—emotion, attitude, and motivation—must be engaged". The learning performance comes after joining the school while choice for English medium school is a situation of taking decision to join the English medium school. In both the cases cognitive and affective aspects of motivation play an important role. In this perspective it can be assumed that English medium school chosen on the bases of motivational aspects will also facilitate the learning performance of the students. The motivational aspects influencing the choice for English medium school are closely associated with better prospects which, beyond any doubt, will facilitate the learning performance of the students. Here it would be worthwhile to discuss about English medium schools.

An English medium system is one that uses English as the medium of instruction, particularly where English is not the native language (Dearden, 2014; Parruck, Ghosh, Sheppard, and Sip, 2014). Initially associated with the expansion of English from its homeland in England and the lowlands of Scotland and its spread to the rest of Great Britain and Ireland, the British empire increased the language's spread, as has the increased economic and cultural influences of United States since World War II.

Perception of working knowledge of English yields its high level value as in most of the working environments English language has achieved special prominence. As, for instance, English is very dominant in the world of computing. As a consequence, quite a large number of countries around the world where English is not their native language are inclining towards the use of English as the normal medium of instruction.

The main objective of English medium schools in India is to motivate students by arousing them regarding the importance of English and then gradually helping them to attain their desired goals. The basic objective is to make the students capable of communicating in English. In India English occupies the position of associate official language. It is being taught for many decades and is used widely as a link language in offices. In schools, colleges and universities it is not only a compulsory subject but also a medium of instruction to the larger extent. English is the main language of science and technology and hold the position of a second language in the school curriculum (Graddol, 2006). English language has been assigned the role of library language. Without exception, every secondary school child has to learn English as a subject, usually for seven years but in some cases fewer. At the primary and secondary school level, India has a large private school system complementing the government run schools, with 29% of students receiving private education in the 6-14 years age groups (NIOS web

portal)¹. Most of the post secondary technical schools are also private school.

As per the Annual Status of Education Report (ASER) 2012, 96.5% of all rural children between the ages of 6 and 14 were enrolled in schools. This is the fourth annual survey to report enrolment above 96%. Another report (ASER, 2013) stated that there were 229 million students enrolled in different accredited urban and rural schools of India. From Class I to XII, representing an increase of 23 hundred thousand students over the total enrolment in 2002, and a 19% increase in girls' enrolment. While quantitatively India is inching closer to universal education, the quality of its education has been questioned particularly in its government run school system. It is important to clarify that while there are private schools in India, they are highly regulated in terms of what they can teach, and in what form they can operate. In view of the growing number of enrolment of students and growing importance of English language it is imperative to identify motivational aspects influencing the choice of English medium school. Findings of the study will help in providing better educational services.

Objectives of the Study

1. To identify motivational aspects influencing the choice for English medium schools
2. To explore strength of agreement with the motivational aspects influencing the choice for English medium schools

Hypotheses

- H₁. Both the intrinsic and extrinsic aspects of motivation will influence the choice for English medium school.
 H₂. The extent of agreement for motivational aspects influencing the choice for English medium school will be at high level among the students.

Research Methodology

Methodology of the research is the description of manner in which the research problem is systematically solved. It is a science of studying how research is done scientifically. The investigator took a sequence of steps in a systematic way to solving the research problem along with appropriate logic behind each step.

Research Design

The design of the present research was descriptive in nature in which primary data was collected from the students of secondary level studying in Delhi. Information obtained from these students provided detailed description of the motivational aspects influencing their choice for English medium schools.

¹<https://www.nios.ac.in/>

Variables Under Study: Motivational aspects influencing students' choice for English medium schools.

Type of Data: In the present study Primary data were collected to identify the motivational aspects influencing students' choice for English Medium School.

Data Source: The data was collected from the secondary level students studying in English Medium School of Delhi. Care was taken to cover entire Delhi at the time of selection of schools. Open choice was not available to the investigator. Data were collected from those schools only that were willing to cooperate.

TOOL OF MEASUREMENT: Self developed scale to assess motivational aspects

About the Scale

Name of Scale: Scale for measuring Motivational Aspects Influencing Choice for English Medium School

On the bases of the opinion of experts of education field eleven statements/items related to motivational aspects that influence the choice of English medium school were identified. Experts selected the most relevant items which were arranged on a paper in the form of a questionnaire. Each item has five category responses namely: strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, strongly disagree. Students were required to tick one of them. Data was obtained on all these items then after factor analysis was carried out. These items are listed below.

1. Students want to choose English Medium School just to learn English because it is an influential language in their friendship.
2. A supportive teaching style in English Medium School allows students' freedom which fosters increased student interest, enjoyment, engagement and performance that makes them motivated to choose the school.
3. The main motive, that influences students to choose English Medium School, is to become accepted as a talented child in the society.
4. I would always regret my decision if I had not availed opportunity to choose English Medium School.
5. English Medium Schools are defined to have an academic environment and therefore students feel

academic confidence to choose such a school for study.

6. Children's wishes to choose the English Medium School are just for the fun of learning spoken English.
7. It is felt that English Medium Schools allow some sort of autonomy in the learning process among students and therefore they have increased motivation to choose such school for study.
8. I would still choose English Medium School even if that would mean study for 18 hours a day.
9. Students are motivated to choose English Medium School for study as they believe that they are valued members of a learning community.
10. Students who are very grade oriented, are extrinsically motivated to choose English Medium School to study.
11. Students who desire to learn are intrinsically motivated to choose English Medium School to study.

Table 1.01: Result of Factor Analysis

Item No.	Components		
	1	2	3
1	.783	-.164	.214
2	.718	.237	.007
3	.663	.296	-.038
4	.587	.299	.039
5	.528	.464	-.108
6	.129	-.024	.872
7	.259	.610	.204
8	-.087	.566	.508
9	.102	.739	.064
10	.305	.632	-.210
11	.132	.533	.072

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis,

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization

Table 1.02: Factor-wise Description of Items

Factors	Item Nos.
Extrinsic Motivation (Component 1)	1,2,3,4,5
Intrinsic Motivation (Component 2)	7,8,9,10,11

Component 3 was not considered a factor as it contained only one item, moreover extent of agreement of the students with this item was very low.

Table 1.03: Scoring System

Response	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Marks	5	4	3	2	1

Reliability

The considerations of reliability and validity typically are viewed as essential elements for determining the quality of any standardized test. However, professional and practitioner associations frequently have placed these

concerns within broader contexts when developing standards and making overall judgments about the quality of any standardized test as a whole within a given context. For establishing the internal consistency reliability: Cronbach's alpha was estimated.

Table 1.04: Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	899	99.9
	Excluded ^a	1	.1
	Total	900	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.767	11

Validity

Content (Face and logical) validity of the scale was verified by number of experts, academicians and professionals. Good correspondence was found to exist between the scale results and the considered judgments of experienced observers.

Sample Design

Sample Size: In all 900 students studying in 6th to 8th class constituted the sample of the present study. Below is the description of sample.

Name of School	Respondents		Total
	Male	Female	
1. MCD School, North-East Delhi	50	50	100
2. Bharat National Public School, East Delhi	50	50	100
3. Gardenia School, East Delhi	50	50	100
4. Govt. Boys Sr. Secondary School, North-East Delhi	50	50	100
5. Scholar School, South Delhi	50	50	100
6. RajdhaniSchool, North-West Delhi	50	50	100
7. Devine Happy School, North-east Delhi	50	50	100
8. LalMandirSchool, West Delhi	50	50	100
9. SKR Public School, Central Delhi	50	50	100
Total	900		

Sample Type: Systematic random sampling method was used in each school

Sample Frame: Sample frame refers to the information regarding whereabouts of the sample units to be selected. The roll list of the students was used as the sample frame.

Sample Extent: Secondary/Senior secondary English medium school located in Delhi

Sample Testing: The questionnaire was administered on small groups of students. After selecting all sample units through the aforesaid method, the investigator took

them in a separate room arranged by the school administration. After distributing questionnaire to each respondent, the investigator explained instructions clearly and asked to clear doubt, if any. When respondents replied that they have understood all the instructions, the investigator gave a signal to start filling up the questionnaire. Data thus obtained pooled group wise and statistically treated with the help of factor analysis and chi square

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Motivation can occur with an idea, observation, need, emotion, or organic state that stimulate person towards the source of fulfillment of the need. Literature in Educational psychology contains enough evidences about the classifications of motivation. Basically there are two categories: One intrinsic motivation and second extrinsic. Intrinsic motivation stimulate due to its inherent interests, for self-fulfillment, enjoyment and to achieve mastery. The extrinsic motivation stimulate person to perform and succeed for the sake of accomplishing a specific result or outcome. Students who are very much grade-oriented are extrinsically motivated, whereas students who seem to truly embrace their work and take a genuine interest in it are intrinsically motivated. In the choice process both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation play important role. As per the results of factor analysis item no. 1,2,3,4, and 5 pertained to extrinsic motivation and item no. 7,8,9,10, and 11 pertain to intrinsic motivation. Item wise analysis of each item was carried out that include meaning and interpretation of the statement, analysis of extent of agreement of the respondents with the statement and assessment of significance of difference between agreed and disagreed

responses with the help of chi square test. Description is given below:

“Students want to choose English Medium School just to learn English because it is an influential language in their friendship”.

Table 2.01: Observed and Expected Frequencies of the Responses and the Value of Chi Square

Level of Agreement	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Strongly Agree	75(8.3%)	180 (20%)	-122.0
Agree	325 (36.1%)	180 (20%)	06.0
Undecided	187 (20.8%)	180 (20%)	-85.0
Disagree	216 (24.0%)	180 (20%)	153.0
Strongly Disagree	97(10.8%)	180 (20%)	-122.0

N=900, Value of Chi Square= 223.800, df= 4, Sig.=000

Students showed their agreement with the item/statement- Students want to choose English Medium School just to learn English because it is an influential language in their friendship. Table 2.01 reveals that the percentage of strongly agreed and agreed respondents (8.3%+36.1%= 44.4%) is much higher than the percentage of strongly disagreed and disagreed (10.8%+24.0%=34.8%) respondents. The difference is significant beyond the 0.01 level of significance. The extent of agreement with this statement is diagrammatically depicted in figure 2.01 which also show a higher level of agreement.

“A supportive teaching style in English Medium School allows students’ freedom which fosters increased student interest, enjoyment, engagement and performance that makes them motivated to choose the school”.

Table 2.02: Observed and Expected Frequencies of the Responses and the Value of Chi Square

Level of Agreement	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Strongly Agree	145(16.1%)	180 (20%)	-35.0
Agree	484 (53.8%)	180 (20%)	304.0
Undecided	168 (18.7%)	180 (20%)	-12.0
Disagree	72 (8.0%)	180 (20%)	-108.0
Strongly Disagree	31(3.4%)	180 (20%)	-149.0

N=900, Value of Chi Square= 709.167, df= 4, Sig.=000

The above item/statement is concerned with the observation that the teaching style of teachers of English medium school is usually supportive in nature. Here the supportive teaching style of teachers is a motivating element. Table 2.02 reveals that majority of respondents are agree with this statement. Ignoring the undecided group we find in table 2.02 that the percentage of strongly agreed and agreed respondents (16.1%+53.8%=69.9%) is much higher than the percentage of strongly disagreed and disagreed (3.4%+8.0%=11.4%) respondents. The difference is significant beyond the 0.01 level of significance. It is, therefore, plausible to conclude that the supportive teaching style of the teachers serve as motivating element to choose English medium school to study. The extent of agreement with the statement is diagrammatically depicted in figure 2.02.

“The main motive, that influences students to choose English Medium School, is to become accepted as a talented child in the society”.

Table 2.03: Observed and Expected Frequencies of the Responses and the Value of Chi Square

Level of Agreement	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Strongly Agree	167 (18.6)	180 (20)	-13.0
Agree	412 (45.8%)	180 (20)	232.0
Undecided	163 (18.1%)	180 (20)	-17.0
Disagree	127 (14.1%)	180 (20)	53.0
Strongly Disagree	31 (3.4%)	180 (20)	149.

N=900, Value of Chi Square= 440.511, df= 4, Sig.=000

the motivating element. The extent of agreement with the statement is exhibited in table 2.03 which illumine that majority favors statement. Disdaining the undecided group, we find in table 2.03 that the percentage of strongly agreed and agreed respondents (18.6%+45.8%=64.4%) is much higher than the percentage of strongly disagreed and disagreed (3.4%+14.1%=17.5%) respondents. The difference is significant beyond the 0.01 level of significance. It is, therefore, reasonable to conclude that the desire to acquire talents serve as motivating element to choose English medium school to study. In other words we can say that the English medium schools maintaining an environment conducive to talent acquisition will attract more students. The extent of agreement with the statement is diagrammatically depicted in figure 2.2.

The idea behind choosing English medium school to study is that the child will acquire more talent and will gain acceptance in the society. Here talent acquisition is

“I would always regret my decision if I had not availed opportunity to choose English Medium School”.

Table 2.04: Observed and Expected Frequencies of the Responses and the Value of Chi Square

Level of Agreement	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Strongly Agree	110 (12.2)	180 (20%)	-70.0
Agree	413 (45.9%)	180 (20%)	233.0
Undecided	227 (25.2%)	180 (20%)	47.0
Disagree	107 (11.9%)	180 (20%)	-73.0
Strongly Disagree	43 (4.8%)	180 (20%)	-137.0

N=900, Value of Chi Square= 474.978, df= 4, Sig.=000

remissness when choosing a school for study. Here avoidance motive is operating. Table 2.04 shows the degree of agreement with statement. Ignoring the undecided group we find in table 2.04 that the percentage of strongly agreed and agreed respondents (12.2%+45.9%=58.1%) is much higher than the percentage of strongly disagreed and disagreed (4.8%+11.9%=16.7%) respondents. The difference is significant beyond the 0.01 level of significance. The finding suggests that it is not reasonable to be careless at the time of choosing school to study. The extent of agreement with the statement is diagrammatically depicted in figure 2.04.

The statement suggests being careful at the time of choosing school. Students require avoiding all

“English Medium Schools are defined to have an academic environment and therefore students feel academic confidence to choose such a school for study”.

Table 2.05: Observed and Expected Frequencies of the Responses and the Value of Chi Square

Level of Agreement	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Strongly Agree	166 (18.4)	180 (20%)	-13.8
Agree	423 (47.0%)	180 (20%)	243.2
Undecided	184 (20.4%)	180 (20%)	4.2
Disagree	98 (10.9%)	180 (20%)	-81.8
Strongly Disagree	28 (3.1%)	180 (20%)	-151.8
N=900, Value of Chi Square= 495.488, df= 4, Sig.=000			

The above item/statement is concerned with the observation that English medium schools maintain good academic environment. Candidates feel that studying in

English medium schools will lead to academic quality. Here gaining academic confidence in English medium schools is a motivating element. Table 2.05 reveals that majority of respondents are agree with this statement. Ignoring the undecided group we find in table 2.05 that the percentage of strongly agreed and agreed respondents (18.4%+47.0%= 65.4%) is much higher than the percentage of strongly disagreed and disagreed (3.1%+10.9%=14.0%) respondents. The difference is significant beyond the 0.01 level of significance. It is, therefore, concluded that the perception of gaining academic confidence in English medium schools serve as motivating element in choice process. The extent of agreement with the statement is diagrammatically depicted in figure 2.05.

“Children’s wishes to choose English medium school are just for the fun”.

Table 2.06: Observed and Expected Frequencies of the Responses and the Value of Chi Square

Level of Agreement	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Strongly Agree	58(6.4%)	180 (20%)	-122.0
Agree	186 (20.6%)	180 (20%)	06.0
Undecided	265 (29.4%)	180 (20%)	-85.0
Disagree	333 (37.0%)	180 (20%)	153.0
Strongly Disagree	58(6.4%)	180 (20%)	-122.0
N=900, Value of Chi Square= 335.767, df= 4, Sig.=000			

The statement is concerned with fun loving which is not a motivating element to choose English medium school. Table 2.06 reveals that majority of respondents are disagree with this statement. Ignoring the undecided group we find in table 2.06 that the percentage of strongly disagreed and disagreed respondents (6.4%+37.0%= 43.4%) is much higher than the percentage of strongly agreed and agreed (6.4%+20.6%= 27.0%) respondents. The difference is significant beyond the 0.01 level of significance. It is, therefore, concluded that students do not choose English medium school just for the fun. The extent of agreement/disagreement is diagrammatically depicted in figure 2.06.

“It is felt that English Medium Schools allow some sort of autonomy in the learning process among students and therefore they have increased motivation to choose such school for study”.

Table 2.07: Observed and Expected Frequencies of the Responses and the Value of Chi Square

Level of Agreement	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Strongly Agree	87 (9.7%)	180 (20%)	-93.0
Agree	389 (43.2%)	180 (20%)	209.0
Undecided	254 (28.2%)	180 (20%)	74.0
Disagree	143 (15.9%)	180 (20%)	-37.0
Strongly Disagree	27 (3.0%)	180 (20%)	-153.0
N=900, Value of Chi Square= 458.800, df= 4, Sig.=000			

The item indicates the importance of autonomy in learning process among students. Autonomy in learning process is supposed to improve self efficacy and confidence. Table 2.07 reveals that majority of respondents are agree with this statement. Ignoring the undecided group, it can be seen in table 2.07 that the percentage of strongly agreed and agreed respondents (9.7%+43.2%= 52.9%) is much higher than the percentage of strongly disagreed and disagreed (3.0%+15.9%=18.9%) respondents. The difference is significant beyond the 0.01 level of significance. It is, therefore, concluded that autonomy in the learning process among students in English medium schools served as motivating element in choice process. The extent of agreement with the statement is diagrammatically depicted in figure 2.07.

“I would still choose English Medium School even if that would mean study for 18 hours a day”.

Table 2.08: Observed and Expected Frequencies of the Responses and the Value of Chi Square

Level of Agreement	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Strongly Agree	101 (11.2%)	180 (20%)	-79.0
Agree	252 (28.0%)	180 (20%)	72.0
Undecided	256 (28.4%)	180 (20%)	76.0
Disagree	198 (22.0%)	180 (20%)	18.0
Strongly Disagree	93 (10.3%)	180 (20%)	-87.0
N=900, Value of Chi Square= 139.411, df= 4, Sig.=000			

Students showed their agreement with the item/statement- I would still choose English Medium School even if that would mean study for 18 hours a day. Table 10.01 reveals that the percentage of strongly agreed and agreed respondents (11.2%+28.0%= 39.2%) is much higher than the percentage of strongly disagreed and disagreed (10.3%+22.0%=32.3%) respondents. The difference is significant beyond the 0.01 level of significance. The extent of agreement with this statement is diagrammatically depicted in figure 2.08 which also show a higher level of agreement.

Students are motivated to choose English Medium School for study as they believe that they are valued members of a learning community”.

Table 2.09: Observed and Expected Frequencies of the Responses and the Value of Chi Square

Level of Agreement	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Strongly Agree	151 (16.8%)	180 (20%)	-29.0
Agree	352 (39.1%)	180 (20%)	172.0
Undecided	186 (20.7%)	180 (20%)	6.0
Disagree	176 (19.6%)	180 (20%)	-4.0
Strongly Disagree	35 (3.9%)	180 (20%)	-145.0
N=900, Value of Chi Square= 285.122, df= 4, Sig.=000			

sense choosing the English medium school for study is the best decision. Majority of respondents showed agreement with this notion. A perusal of table 2.09 reveals that the percentage of strongly agreed and agreed respondents (16.8%+39.1%= 55.9%) is much higher than the percentage of strongly disagreed and disagreed (3.9%+19.6%=23.5%) respondents, the undecided group represents merely 20.7% portion. The difference is significant beyond the 0.01 level of significance. The finding suggests that choosing the English medium schools for study is the best decision in the mind of students. The extent of agreement with this notion is diagrammatically depicted in figure 2.09.

With a belief of valued member of learning community person wants to do the best possible things. In this

“Students, who are very grade oriented, are extrinsically motivated to choose English Medium School to study”.

Table 2.10: Observed and Expected Frequencies of the Responses and the Value of Chi Square

Level of Agreement	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Strongly Agree	173 (19.2)	180 (20%)	-7.0
Agree	412 (45.8%)	180 (20%)	232.0
Undecided	172 (19.1%)	180 (20%)	-8.0
Disagree	112 (12.4%)	180 (20%)	-68.0
Strongly Disagree	31 (3.4%)	180 (20%)	-149.0
N=900, Value of Chi Square= 448.678, df= 4, Sig.=000			

Students, who are grade oriented, seek autonomy in the learning process to enhance academic confidence. Their orientation towards higher academic performance motivates them to choose English medium school. It is general perception of people and also evident from

findings of present investigation that learning environment of English medium schools is conducive to acquire talents by means of supportive teaching style of teachers and availability of other facilities. Extent of agreement with this point of view is demonstrated in table 2.10 which reveals that majority of respondents are agreeing with it. Disregarding the undecided group we find in table 2.10 that the percentage of strongly agreed and agreed respondents (19.2%+45.8%= 65.0%) is much higher than the percentage of strongly disagreed and disagreed (3.4%+12.4%=15.8%) respondents. The difference is significant beyond the 0.01 level of significance. It is, therefore, tenable to conclude that grade orientation of students is a motivating element to choose English medium schools. The extent of agreement with the statement is diagrammatically depicted in figure 2.10.

“Students who desire to learn are intrinsically motivated to choose English Medium School to study”.

Table 2.11: Observed and Expected Frequencies of the Responses and the Value of Chi Square

Level of Agreement	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Strongly Agree	115 (12.8%)	180 (20%)	-65.0
Agree	381 (42.3%)	180 (20%)	201.0
Undecided	232 (25.8%)	180 (20%)	52.0
Disagree	143 (15.9%)	180 (20%)	-37.0
Strongly Disagree	29 (3.2%)	180 (20%)	-151.0
N=900, Value of Chi Square= 397.222, df= 4, Sig.=000			

learn. Table 2.11 reveals that the majority of respondents are in agreement with statement. Ignoring the undecided group we find in table 2.11 that the percentage of strongly agreed and agreed respondents (12.8%+42.3% = 55.1%) is much higher than the percentage of strongly disagreed and disagreed (3.2%+15.9% = 19.1%) respondents. The difference is significant beyond the 0.01 level of significance. The finding suggests that there is an intrinsic motivation to choose English Medium School to study among the students who desire to learn. Figure 2.11 is the diagrammatic presentation of extent of agreement with the statement.

Desire of learning is intrinsic motivation and students feel that English medium school is a better place to

With these findings objective 1 and 2 are met and the hypotheses H_1 and H_2 are accepted.

CONCLUSION

Findings of the study reveal that intrinsic as well as extrinsic motivational aspects are important in the choice process for English medium school. If the school management take care of these aspects, it will motivate students to choose their school. Selection of school influenced by motivational aspects will keep students motivated and their learning performance will also be better. Studies show that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation play an important role in the academic performance of the students (Gbollie and Keamu, 2017).

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